

Deliverable 4.1

CA20104 –

Network on evidence-based physical activity in old age [PhysAgeNet]

Logo

Avatar

ACTION Status

- CSO approval: 25/05/2021
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This document describes and explains the design and set up of standard tools for internal and external communication, including logo, website and social media accounts. It is related to the PhysAgeNet (below- Action) Task 4.1. - establish internal communication (contact and mailing lists, reporting and planning schedules) of all network activities, continuous screening of all minutes / reports for ad-hoc and strategic dissemination and exploitation.

During the first six month of the Action several activities have been accomplished. **Beneath reporting activities, we chose the table format in order to present quick overview of the communication channels, their purpose and how start using them. This should support initial and new members of the Action.**

Therefore, update are planned once in a while.

<p>Contact list</p>	<p>A contact list, including all members of the Action has been created. The data from eCOST system on MC and WG membership were exported as Excel files and information was shared for WG steering teams as well as for mailing lists updates.</p> <p>The contact list includes persons` full name, title, gender, e-mail address, affiliation, as well as information about the membership status, research experience and representing country.</p> <p>The contact list will be updated at least twice a year by the action`s Core Group. It relates to the Task 4.3 (explore requirements and opportunities for perpetuating the network partly or as a whole (e.g. collaboration and connection with universities, other networks or societies, business), including sustainability strategy and action planning, stakeholder analysis and balanced scorecard) and Deliverable 4.3 (report on PhysAgeNet composition, development and sustainability, including status and strategy, CBO 1, CBO 2). Please, see separate Excel file: https://rsuedulv.sharepoint.com/:x/s/PhysAgeNet/ETVv-3gYMNZChQJD7WilJ_0BvZKXOeqZVSFjF3-cz2vBnQ?e=4O8qth .</p> <p>The contact list is processed and distributed by the Action chair. While the Excel format allows for sorting data and quick overview, it is not appropriate for reading motivation and contribution offers of new WG / MC participants.</p>
<p>Mailing lists</p>	<p>Several mailing lists created- for Management Committee, Core Group, Working Groups.</p> <p>physagenet-mc@uni-muenster.de physagenet-cg@uni-muenster.de physagenet-wg1@uni-muenster.de physagenet-wg2@uni-muenster.de physagenet-wg3@uni-muenster.de physagenet-wg4@uni-muenster.de</p> <p>These lists have been set up as a quick communication tool at the start of the Action. They are run by the GH (Uni Münster) and updated from the eCOST-contact list (above).</p> <p>Once MS Teams (below) will be established for daily work, the lists should be reviewed and evaluated, in order to avoid competing communication tools, leading to confusion.</p>
<p>Questionnaire to explore</p>	<p>Questionnaire to explore preferences for communication tools among action members was created and circulated among all MC members before the MC meeting in Piran, Slovenia (April 5 and 6, 2022).</p>

<p>preferences for communication tools</p>	<p>Based on responses from questionnaire (n= 65), 54% of participants expressed that mailing lists would serve fine as communication channels for the Action while the 48% agreed to need for other channels too (see picture below). Majority of 34 participants, who suggested other channels, preferred MS Teams (61%, see picture below).</p> <p>Email lists have been recently set up for all working groups as well as the core group. Do you think additional channels would be helpful for the communications between smaller groups and/or single persons? 63 responses</p> <p>Additional valuable information from questionnaire was received regarding contacts for potential development of Action, also suggestions for hashtags (to be used in social media) and events related to Actions topic (e.g. conferences).</p>
<p>Internal communication</p>	<p>MS Teams was chosen as channel for internal communication and co-working facilitation. https://teams.microsoft.com/j/team/PhysAgeNet</p> <p>All accounts will be initialised by the WG 4 leader, based on any update of the eCOST contact list (above). The MS Teams system is hosted by Rīga Stradiņš University (Latvia).</p> <p>While MS Teams is the main tool for chat, videoconferencing and file storage, other channels are used for special purposes: e.g. mailing lists are used for general information exchange- actual topics from COST, actual topics related to action activities, (see above). Additional questionnaires are set up for expressing interest in meeting participation, in order to organise online and on-site events.</p>
<p>Logo and website</p>	<p>Several potential designer companies for creating our Actions logo and website were searched and offers/quota from 3 of them were gathered. The procurement procedures took place. The Grant Holder (University of Münster, Germany) decided to give the mandate for the creation of our Action’s website and Logo to “Onno Media” (Turkey, www.onnomedia.com) The designers team from “Onno Media” provided several logo versions, which were viewed and discussed via e-mails and during the MC meeting in Piran,</p>

	<p>Slovenia (April 5 and 6, 2022). You can find the final Logos of our Action here: https://rsuedulv.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/PhysAgeNet/Shared%20Documents/General/Logos%20PhysAgeNet?csf=1&web=1&e=LXKTte</p> <p>The work on website https://physagenet.eu development is continuing, the draft of website structure created. https://rsuedulv.sharepoint.com/:w:/s/PhysAgeNet/website structure</p>
<p>Social media accounts</p>	<p>Accounts on several social media have been created:</p> <p>Twitter: https://twitter.com/physagenet</p> <p>LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/85840776</p> <p>A Facebook Account will be set up at a later stage.</p> <p>Suggestions for hashtags from the ACTION members: #activeaging # sport #activetourism #successful ageing #physical activity #biomarkers #getactive # #mensanaincorpersano #exerciseismedicine #exercise #COST #PhysAge #nowphyage #actionphyage #healthyolder #actionforolder #activityforelderly #activityforsenior #olderadults #livelongerlivebetter #lifequality #healthyaging #stayfitwiththevidence #ca20104 #PhysAgeNet #COSTaction #sciencehealthandmovement #healthyageing #evidencebasedresearch #agedandactive.</p> <p>Main hashtags to be used in all social media posts: #PhysAgeNet #COST #activeaging #exerciseismedicine</p>
<p>Stakeholder analysis matrix</p>	<p>Stakeholder analysis matrix was created after the WG4 meeting in Piran, Slovenia (April 5 and 6, 2022). By the end of April it was circulated among the action members. https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1EX70nuSDt9WpWglqkaF07y5AGqpjrz0v6aafZyhELIM/edit#gid=0</p> <p>Such matrix will allow to collect information about potential stakeholders during the action time and it is related to the Task 4.3 (explore requirements and opportunities for perpetuating the network partly or as a whole (e.g. collaboration and connection with universities, other networks or societies, business), including sustainability strategy and action planning, stakeholder analysis and balanced scorecard) and Deliverable 4.2 (Stakeholder Analysis Matrix, containing a list of stakeholders, their interests and influence on the topic, CBO 2).</p>
<p>PhysAgeNet communication strategy</p>	<p>WG4 in cooperation with the Science Communication Coordinator are responsible for collecting information from the CG and WGs about Actions activities and progress. Based on this information social media posts and website updates will be created (at least once a month).</p>